

Perceptions and Expectations of Generation Z Women Regarding Trees in Turkish Cities

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Abstract

The rapid changes in global population growth and urbanization processes, while expanding the structural areas of cities, adversely affect ecosystems and human psychology. Trees within urban areas play a crucial role, extending beyond their aesthetic and vibrant qualities, by contributing significantly to the urban ecosystem. Furthermore, the presence of trees positively influences human psychology by reducing stress levels.

Urban trees are fundamental elements contributing to the urban ecosystem, urban sustainability, and the quality of life in cities. However, it is essential to recognize the significant role of the thoughts and opinions of residents in ensuring the sustainability of decisions aimed at improving environmental quality. In this context, this study aims to identify the perceptions and expectations of Generation Z women in Turkey regarding the trees in their cities.

The obtained results provide detailed insights into the current state of urban trees, and residents' perceptions, preferences, and expectations. Additionally, participants' responses within the study are evaluated separately based on geographical regions to thoroughly examine whether there is a meaningful difference among these variables.

Noteworthy findings of the research indicate that urban tree planting strategies and practices should be tailored to local conditions and public preferences, considering the widely acknowledged aesthetic, environmental, and psychological benefits of trees, which include enhancing beauty, providing wildlife habitats, and improving air quality.

Key words: Urban trees, perception of urban trees, generation Z

Introduction

Cities are settlements where the needs of society such as housing, transportation, employment, leisure, and entertainment are met. They are characterized by continuous social development, rare agricultural activities, and dense population (Keleş 1998).

Cities can also be defined as systems comprising natural and human-made components. Currently, 55% of the world's population resides in urban areas, and this figure is expected to rise to 68% by 2050. Cities are shaped by public and private investments through spatial and urban planning. Therefore, urban planning is of great importance for the healthy formation and development of cities. (Camacho Cervantes, Morelia, Shondube, Jorge E., Castillo, Alicia, MacGregor Fors 2014; Camacho-Cervantes et al. 2014; Department of Economic and Social Affairs 2019). As highlighted in the research conducted by Grimm et al. (2008), increasing urbanization leads to global-scale problems such as climate change, alterations in land use patterns, the emergence of invasive species, and changes in biogeochemical cycles (Camacho-Cervantes et al. 2014). Particularly, unplanned urbanization leads to the loss of natural resource areas such as forests, agricultural lands, and wetlands. This loss is even greater in rapidly growing urban areas surrounded by forested regions (Jantz, Goetz, and Jantz 2005). Furthermore, the reduction of green spaces within urban areas poses a potential threat to the mental health and well-being of urban residents (White et al. 2013).

A significant component of cities is the presence of open green spaces and the trees within them. Urban trees can be described as the most important and dominant vegetative material that provides social, ecological, and psychological benefits and services to urban residents and the city (Gül, Topay, and Öricü 2012). With the expansion of urban areas, the microclimate of cities undergoes changes. The increase in temperature levels associated with urbanization can be mitigated by the positive effects of urban vegetation. Urban heat island effect leads to temperature rise and air pollution. It has been

observed that the increase in urban vegetation results in a decrease in surface air temperatures in street canyons, road surfaces, and building surfaces (Alkan, Adıgüzel, and Kaya 2017; Loughner et al. 2012). Urban trees and urban green infrastructure play a significant role in providing urban ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and improvement of air quality. Additionally, urban trees create habitats that support the continuity of wildlife within cities, particularly bird species (von Döhren and Haase 2019; Wood and Esaian 2020). A study conducted in the state of California, United States, revealed a positive correlation between the amount of trees in urban areas and human health (Ulmer et al. 2016).

Demographers and researchers commonly define the generation born between 1995 and 2010 as Generation Z (Seemiller and Grace 2017). The Pew Research Center, however, defines the birth range of Generation Z as between the years 1996 and 2012 (Dimock 2019). Courtney (2020), emphasizes that Generation Z consists of individuals born from the mid-1990s to the mid-2000s, who are not yet college graduates but are entering the workforce and beginning to have a voice in elections by voting.

The biggest factor that distinguishes Generation Z from other generations is being born into a time period where technology is widely used. Technology and the internet play a significant role in the daily lives of Generation Z. While previous generations used traditional mass media to keep up with daily events, Generation Z follows this information flow digitally with certainty. Having been introduced to technology from birth, this generation has developed motor skills more than other generations because they are interested in multiple subjects simultaneously. Generation Z lives in close integration with technology in their educational, professional, and social lives. Therefore, they struggle in relationships that require face-to-face communication (İrmak Aydın 2020; Taş, Demirdöğmez, and Küçükoğlu 2017; Turner 2015).

Individuals of Generation Z, who closely monitor the global database formed by the internet, can easily stay informed about the agenda from anywhere in the world. Generation Z, which closely follows the agenda, is highly sensitive to ecology and global values (Howard 2016).

This study evaluates how urban trees in the 81 provinces of Turkey influence the perception of urban residents aged between 13 and 29 (Generation Z). The aim of the study is to determine the positive and negative effects of urban trees on Generation Z, as well as to examine their perceptions of the advantages and disadvantages. Additionally, the study investigates whether the results vary across different cities.

Material and Method

Material

This study was conducted in all 81 provinces of Turkey. The materials of the study, including existing literature, survey forms, and data analysis, were conducted using the IBM SPSS 26 statistical analysis program. Surveys were administered online via Google Forms. Participants were randomly selected Generation Z women from across the country.

Method

The study consists of five stages: literature review, preparation and analysis of survey questions, and general evaluation and conclusion. The methodological flowchart is depicted below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flow chart

The literature review, utilized in the first phase of the research, was employed to determine the research topic by drawing from existing literature on urban trees. Following the literature review, a survey method was considered suitable for the research. The primary aim of this study is to examine how the perception of urban trees in Turkey is shaped by Generation Z women. The survey comprises closed-ended questions focusing on assessing the general condition of urban trees. These questions aim to understand the environmental, social, and economic benefits of trees, as well as the current condition and needs of trees in the participants' respective cities. In the survey, demographic information such as age, education level, monthly income, and city of residence was collected to facilitate a comprehensive analysis of the research findings.

The prepared survey questions were implemented online via Google Forms. The obtained results were statistically analyzed with the assistance of the IBM SPSS 26 program. In the final stage of the study, the results obtained from the survey were evaluated.

Findings

Table 1. Data on demographic information of the participants

		N.	(%)			N.	(%)
City	İstanbul	281	26,4	Profession	Student	713	67,0
	İzmir	214	20,1		Not working	99	9,3
	Ankara	124	11,7		Public employee	65	6,1
	Bursa	50	4,7		Private Sector	173	16,3
	Other	395	37,1		Self-employment	14	1,3
Education level	Primary education	11	1,0	Income Level	0- 2.000 TL	672	63,2
	High School	236	22,2		2.000- 4.000 TL	214	20,1
	University	748	70,3		4.500- 6.000 TL	95	8,9
	Master's Degree	58	5,5		6.000- 8.000 TL	44	4,1
	PhD.	11	1,0		8.000 TL and above	39	3,7

According to the Table 1, the city with the highest number of participants was determined as İstanbul (26.4%). The group with the highest rate in terms of education level is university graduates (70.3%), while those with the lowest rate are master's and doctorate graduates and primary school graduates (both 1.0%). When looking at occupational groups, the group with the highest rate was determined to be students (67.0%), while the group with the lowest rate was determined to be self-employed (1.3%). In terms of income level, the group with the highest rate was determined to be those with an income of 0-2,000 TL (63.2%), while the group with the lowest rate was determined to be those with an income of 8,000 TL and above (3.7%).

Table 2. Data on participants' views on the contribution of trees in urban life

Statements	Mean	Std.
Trees clean the air	6,45	1,44
Trees provide protection from the wind	5,80	1,59
Trees lower the temperature	5,39	1,76
Trees are home to birds and small animals	6,52	1,42
Trees beautify the appearance of a place	6,53	1,42
Trees create space for children to play	6,08	1,61
Trees improve mood and reduce stress	6,43	1,44
Trees provide shade in summer, allowing me to move around outdoors comfortably	6,47	1,43
Trees increase real estate value on the street where they are located	5,40	1,79
Trees have economic value	4,95	2,03
Trees make hiking a pleasure	6,47	1,45
Afforested streets have a positive impact on urban life	6,49	1,46

Participants showed the highest rate of agreement with the statements "Trees beautify the appearance of the place where they are located" (6.53) and "Trees provide a home for birds and small animals" (6.52). On the other hand, "Trees lower the temperature" (5.39) and "Trees increase real estate value on the street where they are located" (5.40) has lowest rate of agreement.

Table 3. Data on participants' views on the importance and development of trees in urban life

Statements	Mean	Std.
It is important for me to have trees on the streets of the city I live in	6,35	1,43
The trees on the streets of the city where I live are useful	6,19	1,54
The number of trees in my city is sufficient	3,18	1,95
The trees in my city are made up of different species	4,43	1,85
The number of trees in my city should be increased	6,34	1,48
Trees in my city should be better maintained	6,04	1,59
The species diversity of trees in my city should be increased	6,17	1,52
Afforested areas are sufficient in the city where I live	3,06	1,98
More trees should be planted in residential areas in the city where I live	6,24	1,55

According to the data evaluating the views of the participants on the importance and development of trees in urban life, the highest level of participation was determined as "It is important for me to have trees on the streets of the city where I live" (6,35) and "The number of trees in my city should be increased" (6,34). The least participation was determined as "The afforested areas in the city where I live are sufficient" (3,06) and "The number of trees in the city where I live is sufficient" (3,18) (Table 3).

Table 4. Participants' data on the negative environmental effects of trees in urban life

Statements	Mean	Std.
Falling leaves from trees cause blockages in sewers	3,16	1,63
Trees make the street look dirty	1,36	0,85
Trees cause allergies	3,19	1,65
Trees attract unwanted insects and animals	3,14	1,72
Trees cause lightning strikes	2,73	1,59
Trees take up a lot of space on the street	1,50	0,99
Tree roots damage roads/sidewalks	1,71	1,20
Trees block traffic signs	1,95	1,33
Trees blend into street lamps and lampposts	2,04	1,35
Trees fall and cause damage	2,13	1,43
Trees create uncanny space	1,69	1,15
Trees block the view of the cityscape	1,46	0,98

In examining the data presented in Table 4 regarding the Negative Environmental Impacts of Trees in Urban Life, it was found that the highest levels of agreement among participants were for the statements "Trees cause allergies" (3.19) and "Falling leaves from trees cause blockages in sewers" (3.16). Conversely, the statements "Trees block the view of the cityscape" (1.46) and "Trees take up a lot of space on the street" (1.50) had the lowest levels of agreement.

Table 5. Data on participants' views on the contribution of trees in urban life by city

Statements	City	N	Mean	Std.	Sig.	Statements	City	N	Ort.	SS.	Sig.
Trees clean the air	İstanbul	281	6,41	1,53	0,436**	Trees improve mood and reduce stress	İstanbul	281	6,40	1,53	0,032**
	İzmir	214	6,54	1,37			İzmir	214	6,44	1,40	
	Ankara	124	6,57	1,18			Ankara	124	6,69	1,05	
	Bursa	50	6,38	1,51			Bursa	50	6,08	1,69	
	Other	395	6,41	1,47			Other	395	6,41	1,48	
Trees provide protection from the wind	İstanbul	281	5,75	1,67	0,085**	Trees provide shade in summer, allowing me to move around outdoors comfortably	İstanbul	281	6,42	1,54	0,208**
	İzmir	214	5,78	1,61			İzmir	214	6,50	1,39	
	Ankara	124	6,07	1,40			Ankara	124	6,68	1,10	
	Bursa	50	5,52	1,63			Bursa	50	6,30	1,56	
	Other	395	5,79	1,57			Other	395	6,44	1,46	
Trees lower the temperature	İstanbul	281	5,40	1,84	0,070*	Trees increase real estate value on the street where they are located	İstanbul	281	5,51	1,88	0,155*
	İzmir	214	5,57	1,70			İzmir	214	5,36	1,80	
	Ankara	124	5,54	1,64			Ankara	124	5,67	1,65	
	Bursa	50	4,86	1,83			Bursa	50	5,12	2,06	
	Other	395	5,31	1,76			Other	395	5,29	1,71	
Trees are home to birds and small animals	İstanbul	281	6,48	1,52	0,063**	Trees have economic value	İstanbul	281	5,16	1,99	0,015*
	İzmir	214	6,59	1,36			İzmir	214	5,12	1,96	
	Ankara	124	6,69	1,13			Ankara	124	5,11	2,10	
	Bursa	50	6,38	1,51			Bursa	50	4,50	2,12	
	Other	395	6,47	1,45			Other	395	4,73	2,05	
Trees beautify the appearance of a place	İstanbul	281	6,49	1,52	0,495**	Trees make hiking a pleasure	İstanbul	281	6,45	1,52	0,830**
	İzmir	214	6,56	1,38			İzmir	214	6,47	1,44	
	Ankara	124	6,72	1,09			Ankara	124	6,62	1,14	
	Bursa	50	6,50	1,52			Bursa	50	6,42	1,55	
	Other	395	6,50	1,45			Other	395	6,44	1,47	
Trees create space for children to play	İstanbul	281	6,04	1,74	0,195**	Afforested streets have a positive impact on urban life	İstanbul	281	6,45	1,52	0,392**
	İzmir	214	6,04	1,59			İzmir	214	6,54	1,46	
	Ankara	124	6,32	1,30			Ankara	124	6,65	1,07	
	Bursa	50	5,76	1,77			Bursa	50	6,40	1,55	
	Other	395	6,11	1,58			Other	395	6,44	1,51	

*One way Anova

**Kruskal Wallis

A significant difference was observed among cities regarding the statement that "trees improve mood and reduce stress" (Ankara: 6.69, İzmir: 6.44, İstanbul: 6.40). In contrast, the view that "trees have economic value" showed similarities between participants in İstanbul and İzmir, while participants in Bursa provided a lower assessment (İstanbul: 5.16, İzmir: 5.12, Bursa: 4.50). No statistically significant differences were observed in the other statements (Table 5).

Table 6. Data on participants' views on the importance and development of trees in urban life by city

Statements	City	N	Mean	Std.	Sig.
It is important for me to have trees on the streets of the city I live in	İstanbul	281	6,17	1,60	0,931**
	İzmir	214	6,17	1,58	
	Ankara	124	6,32	1,28	
	Bursa	50	6,08	1,63	
	Other	395	6,19	1,56	
The trees on the streets of the city where I live are useful	İstanbul	281	6,37	1,47	0,966**
	İzmir	214	6,36	1,39	
	Ankara	124	6,44	1,16	
	Bursa	50	6,40	1,39	
	Other	395	6,30	1,52	
The number of trees in my city is sufficient	İstanbul	281	2,65	1,88	0,000*
	İzmir	214	3,35	1,94	
	Ankara	124	2,82	1,74	
	Bursa	50	3,44	1,82	
	Other	395	3,55	1,99	
The trees in my city are made up of different species	İstanbul	281	3,83	1,91	0,000*
	İzmir	214	4,66	1,82	
	Ankara	124	4,48	1,76	
	Bursa	50	4,58	1,89	
	Other	395	4,71	1,75	
The number of trees in my city should be increased	İstanbul	281	6,43	1,51	0,001**
	İzmir	214	6,32	1,46	
	Ankara	124	6,56	1,20	
	Bursa	50	6,12	1,55	
	Other	395	6,25	1,52	
Trees in my city should be better maintained	İstanbul	281	6,11	1,61	0,004**
	İzmir	214	6,10	1,53	
	Ankara	124	6,31	1,34	
	Bursa	50	6,04	1,48	
	Other	395	5,87	1,67	
The species diversity of trees in my city should be increased	İstanbul	281	6,27	1,53	0,006**
	İzmir	214	6,16	1,46	
	Ankara	124	6,42	1,24	
	Bursa	50	5,98	1,53	
	Other	395	6,05	1,61	
Afforested areas are sufficient in the city where I live	İstanbul	281	2,44	1,90	0,000*
	İzmir	214	3,26	1,96	
	Ankara	124	2,69	1,79	
	Bursa	50	3,56	2,06	
	Other	395	3,44	1,98	
More trees should be planted in residential areas in the city where I live	İstanbul	281	6,38	1,531	0,019**
	İzmir	214	6,18	1,588	
	Ankara	124	6,48	1,179	
	Bursa	50	6,18	1,535	
	Other	395	6,12	1,648	

*One way Anova

**Kruskal Wallis

According to the given data, statistically significant differences have been observed among cities regarding the importance and enhancement of trees in urban life. Upon examining the average scores

for each proposition across cities, notable variations among cities are evident in specific areas. In terms of the proposition 'The number of trees in my city is sufficient', the city with the highest average is Other (3.55), followed by Bursa (3.44), İzmir (3.35), Ankara (2.82), and İstanbul (2.65). Regarding the proposition 'The trees in my city are made up of different species', the highest average is attained by İzmir (4.66), followed by Other (4.71), Bursa (4.58), Ankara (4.48), and İstanbul (3.83). For the proposition 'The number of trees in my city should be increased', the highest average is recorded in Ankara (6.56), trailed by İzmir (6.32), Other (6.25), İstanbul (6.43), and Bursa (6.12). In regard to the proposition 'Trees in my city should be better maintained', the highest average is observed in Ankara (6.31), with İstanbul (6.11), İzmir (6.10), Bursa (6.04), and Other (5.87) following suit. Concerning the proposition 'The species diversity of trees in my city should be increased', the highest average is found in Ankara (6.42), followed by İstanbul (6.27), Other (6.05), İzmir (6.16), and Bursa (5.98). Regarding the proposition 'Afforested areas are sufficient in the city where I live', the highest average is seen in İzmir (3.26), trailed by Bursa (3.56), 'Other' (3.44), Ankara (2.69), and lastly İstanbul (2.44). Lastly, for the proposition 'More trees should be planted in residential areas', the highest average is identified in Ankara (6.48), with İstanbul (6.38), Bursa (6.18), İzmir (6.18), and Other (6.12) following in succession (Table 6).

Table 7. Participants' data on the negative environmental impacts of trees in urban life by city data

Statements	City	N	Mean	Std.	Sig.	Statements	City	N	Mean	Std.	Sig.
Falling leaves from trees cause blockages in sewers	İstanbul	281	2,90	1,61	0,003*	Tree roots damage roads/sidewalks	İstanbul	281	1,56	1,16	0,006**
	İzmir	214	3,48	1,62			İzmir	214	1,70	1,10	
	Ankara	124	3,10	1,79			Ankara	124	1,69	1,19	
	Bursa	50	3,22	1,36			Bursa	50	1,82	1,19	
	Diğer	395	3,19	1,61			Diğer	395	1,83	1,27	
Trees make the street look dirty	İstanbul	281	1,35	0,92	0,774**	Trees block traffic signs	İstanbul	281	1,81	1,26	0,070**
	İzmir	214	1,32	0,58			İzmir	214	1,92	1,27	
	Ankara	124	1,33	0,80			Ankara	124	2,16	1,48	
	Bursa	50	1,38	0,70			Bursa	50	2,04	1,28	
	Diğer	395	1,38	0,95			Diğer	395	1,99	1,35	
Trees cause allergies	İstanbul	281	3,02	1,70	0,121**	Trees blend into street lamps and lampposts	İstanbul	281	1,88	1,27	0,080*
	İzmir	214	3,41	1,70			İzmir	214	2,07	1,28	
	Ankara	124	3,27	1,69			Ankara	124	2,22	1,49	
	Bursa	50	3,06	1,46			Bursa	50	1,88	1,12	
	Diğer	395	3,17	1,58			Diğer	395	2,12	1,42	
Trees attract unwanted insects and animals	İstanbul	281	3,01	1,80	0,472*	Trees fall and cause damage	İstanbul	281	1,91	1,31	0,042*
	İzmir	214	3,18	1,68			İzmir	214	2,21	1,49	
	Ankara	124	3,34	1,76			Ankara	124	2,27	1,50	
	Bursa	50	3,02	1,55			Bursa	50	2,02	1,13	
	Diğer	395	3,15	1,69			Diğer	395	2,21	1,47	
Trees cause lightning strikes	İstanbul	281	2,60	1,58	0,288*	Trees create uncanny space	İstanbul	281	1,63	1,13	0,464**
	İzmir	214	2,76	1,54			İzmir	214	1,77	1,14	
	Ankara	124	2,85	1,69			Ankara	124	1,69	1,23	
	Bursa	50	2,44	1,37			Bursa	50	1,66	0,98	
	Diğer	395	2,80	1,62			Diğer	395	1,70	1,17	
Trees take up a lot of space on the street	İstanbul	281	1,43	0,94	0,353*	Trees block the view of the cityscape	İstanbul	281	1,41	0,92	0,033**
	İzmir	214	1,47	0,90			İzmir	214	1,48	0,97	
	Ankara	124	1,44	0,97			Ankara	124	1,36	1,03	
	Bursa	50	1,52	0,81			Bursa	50	1,44	0,79	
	Diğer	395	1,58	1,09			Diğer	395	1,52	1,02	

*One way Anova

**Kruskal Wallis

The provided table presents data regarding participants' perceptions of the adverse environmental effects of trees in urban life across different cities. Statistical differences exist among propositions within

the table. Specifically, "Falling leaves from trees cause blockages in sewers", "Tree roots damage roads/sidewalks", "Trees fall and cause damage", and "Trees block the view of the cityscape" stand out as propositions with notable variations. In terms of "Falling leaves from trees cause blockages in sewers", the mean scores across cities vary. İzmir (3.48) and the other (3.19) demonstrate the highest mean scores, followed by Bursa (3.22), Ankara (3.10), and İstanbul (2.90). Regarding the proposition "Tree roots damage roads/sidewalks", Bursa (1.82) yields the highest mean score, followed by the other category (1.83), Ankara (1.69), İzmir (1.70), and İstanbul (1.56). Similarly, for the propositions "Trees fall and cause damage" and "Trees block the view of the cityscape", significant discrepancies are apparent among cities. The mean scores for "Trees fall and cause damage" are as follows: İzmir (1.49), Ankara (1.50), İstanbul (1.31), other (1.47), and Bursa (1.13). For "Trees block the view of the cityscape", the mean scores are as follows: Other (1.52), Bursa (1.44), İzmir (1.48), İstanbul (1.41), and Ankara (1.36).

Results and Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the multifaceted benefits of urban trees as perceived by Generation Z women in Turkey. Participants generally acknowledge the aesthetic, environmental, and psychological benefits of trees. Particularly, there is a widespread belief in their role in enhancing the beauty of places, providing habitats for wildlife, and improving air quality. These benefits are highly valued across different cities.

According to the survey results, Generation Z women express significant appreciation for various contributions of trees to urban life. Trees are valued for cleaning the air (mean = 6.45), providing protection from the wind (mean = 5.80), lowering temperatures (mean = 5.39), and serving as habitats for birds and small animals (mean = 6.52). Furthermore, trees are appreciated for their ability to beautify urban areas (mean = 6.53), create play spaces for children (mean = 6.08), improve mood and reduce stress (mean = 6.43), provide shade (mean = 6.47), and enhance real estate value (mean = 5.40). These findings suggest a strong positive perception of trees' role in urban environments.

Across Turkey, Generation Z women express a desire for more trees and better maintenance in their cities. Many urban areas are deemed insufficient in terms of tree numbers and green spaces. Despite recognizing the benefits, participants also acknowledge some negative impacts, such as leaf litter causing blockages in sewers and tree roots damaging roads and sidewalks. However, these issues are generally viewed as less significant compared to the overarching benefits provided by urban trees.

Generation Z women across Turkey express a significant desire for increased tree coverage and improved maintenance of urban green spaces. Many urban areas are perceived as deficient in both the number of trees and the extent of green spaces available. Therefore, urban trees are seen as indispensable elements for sustainable and livable cities.

However, it is critical to consider the unique perceptions and expectations of the public in different cities. The study reveals that each city has distinct needs and priorities concerning urban forestry. Consequently, tree planting strategies and maintenance practices should be customized to address local conditions and public demands. For example, İstanbul might prioritize diversifying tree species, Bursa might focus on selecting appropriate locations for tree planting, and cities like İzmir could enhance their tree maintenance activities.

By tailoring urban forestry practices to the specific needs of each city, the benefits of urban trees can be maximized while minimizing any potential negative impacts. Therefore, the formulation and implementation of tree planting policies for sustainable and livable cities should be informed by local requirements and public preferences.

In conclusion, urban forestry policies must be adaptive and responsive to the distinct ecological and social contexts of each city to optimize the contributions of urban trees to urban sustainability and livable.

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